

THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING ON ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE IN YEMENI PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

Strategic planning is crucial for organizational excellence in higher education. This study examines the relationship between strategic planning and organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities. The primary objectives of this research were to: (1) assess the impact of strategic planning on organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities, (2) evaluate the current level of strategic planning practices and its dimensions, and (3) determine the level of organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities located in Sana'a, the capital city. To achieve these objectives, a quantitative approach was employed, encompassing both descriptive and analytical methods. A structured questionnaire was distributed to a sample of 317 academic and administrative leaders from five Yemeni private universities in Sana'a. The comprehensive inventory method was utilized to gather comprehensive data. The findings revealed a remarkably high level of strategic planning attainment among the sampled universities. Additionally, a statistically significant positive correlation was established between strategic planning and organizational excellence. Furthermore, statistically significant differences in strategic planning practices were observed among the study participants, with variations attributed to the size of the university. Based on these findings, the study recommends a heightened emphasis on strategic planning to foster organizational excellence within the Yemeni private university sector.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, Organizational Excellence, Yemeni Private Universities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational excellence is one of the most important and modern topics, as standards of excellence have become at the forefront of the goals that organizations seek to achieve to support more excellence and uniqueness in their organizational performance. Which requires administrative leaders to make efforts to achieve success and progress.

Achieving organizational excellence with all its standards and indicators is based on strategic planning in building a sound and solid foundation for all its components represented by planning policies, and systems, developing structures, planning operations, investing resources, and developing human and material capabilities in a way that achieves the organization's goals and allows it the ability to conduct organizational analysis. And updating it regularly, with the aim of continuous development and improvement (Al-Douri, 2010, p. 41).

It expresses the organization's exploitation of available opportunities within the framework of effective strategic planning, and the commitment to realize a common vision dominated by clarity of purpose, adequacy of resources, and keenness on performance (Aporia, 2014, p. 3). Strategic planning, at both the scientific and applied levels, has witnessed great development and has become a core specialty in many colleges of management in various universities, as many academics and managers

have developed many models and frameworks to assist in making strategic decisions in the context of complex, highly competitive environments (Hussein and Abbas, 2018, p. 5). Numerous studies, including one by Bouirihia (2022): The study aimed to shed light on the impact of strategic planning on organizational excellence in the Directorate of Electricity Distribution in Ghardaia. The study concluded that there is a correlation between strategic planning and organizational excellence in the Directorate of Distribution and Electricity in Ghardaia. A study by Eid (2019), aimed to identify the impact of strategic awareness on achieving institutional excellence in Egyptian universities in light of organizational commitment as a mediating variable. The study found that there is a noticeable decrease in the degree of strategic awareness, and there are mutual environmental relationships between the dimensions of strategic awareness on institutional excellence.

A study by Saeed & et.al (2019) aimed to know the impact of strategic management and organizational culture on organizational excellence in the organization, and the study reached several results, the most important of which are: that strategic management and organizational culture were positive, and that they had an important impact on organizational excellence. And Study Clay, et. al, (2016), the study aimed to identify the link between the formal strategic planning process, strategic planning flexibility, and the ability to innovate with the performance of companies, and it reached several results, the most important of which is: that formal strategic planning processes and strategic planning flexibility are positively related to performance Organizations.

A study by Santana & et. al (2013), the study aimed to know the extent to which strategic planning contributes to the performance of Brazilian universities in the state of Pará. The study reached several results, the most important of which are: The first university has completed nearly all the steps of the strategic planning process and has contributed positively to achieving the goals. The organization and the second university were unable to contribute to achieving the goals positively. Yemeni private universities, like other universities, are in greatest need of strategic planning, as they are organizations that work in the field of finance and business and an environment characterized by instability and change in attitudes. This makes it vulnerable to the risks of crises locally and globally. It is also currently subject to factors of continuous development and growth. Many right-wing private universities have opened in recent years. This requires these universities to strive to apply modern concepts in administrative literature, especially since these universities are also living in the shadow of multiple revolutions in various fields, including the information, communications and technology revolutions.

At the same time, there has been development in modern concepts, especially in the field of quality and academic accreditation. Therefore, these universities need to employ everything new in management in a way that contributes to developing and achieving organizational excellence. With strategic planning, Yemeni private universities can advance and compete, using the limited resources and available competencies that enable them to improve organizational effectiveness, improve performance, and achieve organizational excellence. over its competitors according to scientifically studied methods.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A: Strategic planning

Strategic planning in educational organizations is a necessity and not a luxury because it leads to raising the performance of educational organizations now and in the future if it is applied well. It is the development and formation of long-term plans to deal effectively with the opportunities and threats present in the external environment surrounding the organization, in light of the sources of strength and weakness of the resources. Which the organization has in its internal environment (Hunger & Wheelen, 1997, p. 10). Strategic planning has been defined as the appropriate and appropriate method for determining long-term goals and the actual direction of the organization in achieving its goals (Policastro, 2003, p.1). Strategic planning is defined as the process of developing the organization's mission, goals, strategic plans, and policies to achieve an orderly transition from a current situation to a targeted future situation (Garger, 2015, p. 194). Educational institutions often rely on three dimensions in strategic planning The first dimension is environmental analysis: It is defined as the process of reviewing both the external environment to identify the most important challenges facing the organization and the internal environment to identify the most important strengths and weaknesses of the organization (Hamedi et al., 2021, p. 17). Environmental analysis has been defined as the key to strategic planning in terms of identifying the internal environment (strengths and weaknesses) to determine the organization's efficiency and distinct capabilities, and analyzing the external environment to identify (opportunities and threats) that the organization may face in the future, and identifying the competitive position and share. Marketability compared to other organizations (Hunger & Wheelen, 1997, p. 53). The second dimension is strategic orientation. The strategic leader can see the future of the organization in a clear and integrated way (Mohyaldeen & Alamri 2023, p. 235). Strategic orientation has been defined as an analytical process for choosing the future location of the organization according to the changes occurring in its external environment and the extent of the organization's adaptation to them (Omar, 2019, p. 10). The third dimension of strategy formulation: is the process of selecting an alternative from a group of available alternatives that is commensurate with the organization's capabilities and capabilities and is characterized by flexibility and responsiveness to external environmental variables and the opportunities and threats they bring (Al-Shuaibi, 2004, p. 111). Strategic formulation was defined as: determining the appropriate strategic path (road) for the organization, that is, the appropriate strategic alternatives at the level of the organization and the sector, and then determining the strategic option to achieve the organization's goals (Al-Ariqi, 2017, p. 9).

B: Organizational Excellence

Organizational excellence and its requirements are among the most important goals and priorities that many university organizations seek to achieve in light of a changing environment. It is achieved through planning, preparation, and continuous effort from all members of the organization. The senior management bears a great responsibility in preparing the organizational environment in absorbing the idea of excellence and achieving it on the ground, and this is based on advanced and sophisticated management techniques and methodologies (Qandil, 2020, p. 22) Organizational excellence is defined as a qualitative process in which all departments working in the organization participate to better understand the activities and operations carried out by the organization, and work to address errors and improve processes in it, which

prompts it to improve its effectiveness, increase its competitive strength, and excel in performance (Al-Thaqafi, 2019, p. 64). Organizational excellence has been defined as the progress and growth of the organization in all organizational aspects, and increasing the probability of long-term organizational success, through a logical and rational approach that promotes change, to improve the level of organizational effectiveness, it is a comprehensive approach to improving organizational performance (Dehaghan & Pourtah, 2014, p. 141). The dimensions of organizational is excellence four dimensions:

The first dimension excellence in leadership: It is the most important pillar of modern management that requires superior leadership capabilities to be able to keep pace with developments and changes imposed by the knowledge age (AL.Shobaki & Naser, 2016: 70). Excellence in leadership is defined as how to work in a team and participate in decision-making to achieve the goals of the group and individuals simultaneously through an effective strategy and leadership (Al-Baroudi, 2015, p. 27).

The second dimension is excellence in human resources has been defined as having subordinates possess sufficient skills, abilities, and behaviors to enable them to perform their work effectively, as they present ideas and products characterized by modernity and creativity, in a way that achieves the organization's goals (Al-Shahrani, 2017: p. 43). excellence in human resources is defined as a concept applied to all people or individuals belonging to the organization and working in it, whether they are superiors or subordinates, and these individuals are contracted by the organization to carry out job tasks in exchange for compensation and rewards, provided that these individuals, while carrying out their assigned work, adhere to the organization's strategy and goals (Mohamood & Azhar, 2015, p. 103).

The third dimension: excellence in organizational culture: It is the degree of compatibility of behavior and reflects the excellence of the values and beliefs of influential individuals in the organization, and it includes elements (openness, trust, authenticity, tribal activity, independence, and confrontation with problems), as these elements contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of human performance (Belkebir, 2018, p. 169). Excellence in organizational culture has been defined as the framework that governs, directs and explains the behavior of individuals in the organization, through a set of values, beliefs, basic assumptions, standards and organizational norms in which the members of the organization participate, which directly and indirectly affect the behavior of employees and how they perform their work. Influenced by values And the beliefs held by leaders and officials (Al-Omari, 2017, p. 118). The fourth dimension: excellence in the organizational structure: Is defined as representing the degree of ability of the structural framework that connects the parts of the organization, defines the relationships between businesses, centers and departments, and the expected cooperation between the parts of the organization and clarifies the lines of authority and responsibility in a way that helps in performing various activities to achieve the required goals (Belkebir, 2018, p. 169). Excellence in organizational structure was also defined as relying on an organizational structure characterized by a degree of flexibility to be able to change, exploit opportunities, and quickly make decisions (Zain Al-Abidin & Yassin, 2020, p. 12).

Figure 1: Research model

Study Hypotheses:

Main Hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect for strategic planning in achieving organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities.

From this main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses branch out:

Sub-Hypothesis 1: There is a statistically significant effect of environmental analysis in achieving organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities.

Sub-Hypothesis 2: There is a statistically significant effect of strategic direction in achieving organizational excellence in private Yemeni universities.

Sub-Hypothesis 3: There is a statistically significant effect of strategic formulation in achieving organizational excellence in private Yemeni universities.

3. METHOD

The study targeted leaders (academic and administrative) working in 5 private Yemeni universities (University of Science and Technology, National University, Yemeni University, Sheba University, and Queen Arwa University) in the capital Sana'a. The study adopted a criteria for selecting universities that had been established more than twenty years ago.

The number of colleges must be more than five. It was used to determine the study sample using a comprehensive inventory method of (300) academic and administrative leaders. The study relied on a questionnaire that was distributed to sample members. The study data were analyzed using Smart PSL software.

The study used structural equation modeling using least squares to measure bias in the response of the study sample. It also used frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations, and the relative weight index in descriptive statistics, and structural equation modeling using partial least squares and the one-way variance test.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	247	82.3
	Female	53	17.7
Age	25 years and under	17	5.7
	25-35 years	91	30.3
	36-50 years	177	59.0
	50 years and over	15	5.0
Educational Level	High School or less	5	1.7
	Bachelor's Degree	84	28.0
	Master's Degree	53	17.7
	Doctorate	158	52.7
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	48	16.0
	5-10 years	90	30.0
	11-15 years	125	41.7
	More than 15 years	37	12.3
Total		300	100.00

The demographic details of the participants are shown in the table. Of the 300 academic and administrative employees in the sample, there are 247 (.82%) males and 53 (17.7%) females. The majority of participants (59.0%), in terms of age groups, are between 36 and 50 years. In terms of educational attainment, the majority (52.7%) hold a doctorate and in terms of years of experience, the majority of participants (41.7) are between 11-15 years.

4. RESULTS

The preceding table shows the statistical analysis of the strategic planning variable. The results showed that the level of strategic planning practice in the Yemeni private universities under study was very high with an average of (6.301), a standard deviation of (0.822), and a large percentage (90.02%). The dimension of strategic orientation was the highest among the practices. Strategic planning with an average of (6.355) and a standard deviation of (0.828), with a high percentage of (90.79%), which is a percentage considered large.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Strategic Planning Factor

No.	Dimension	Mean Average	Standard deviation	Relative Weight	Linguistic Significance
1	Environmental analysis	6.273	0.840	89.62%	Very High
2	Human resources	6.355	0.828	90.79%	Very High
3	Strategy formulation	6.169	0.973	88.12%	Very High
	Strategic planning	6.301	0.822	90.02%	Very High

This is due to the awareness of the Yemeni private universities under study of the importance of strategic direction and their possession of vision, mission and goals, and because they are also considered among the standards of quality assurance. Academic accreditation is approved by the Academic Accreditation Council and ensures the quality of education, While the dimension (strategy formulation) ranked lowest among strategic planning practices with an average of (6.169) and a standard deviation of (0.973), with a percentage of (88.12%), which is a very high percentage. This is because universities focus their attention on preparing the vision, mission, and goals. Formulating the strategy because it is among the requirements and standards for quality assurance and academic accreditation approved by the Council for Academic Accreditation and Quality Assurance of Education.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Organizational Excellence Factor

No.	Dimensions	Mean Average	Standard deviation	Relative Weight	Linguistic Significance
1	Excellence in leadership	6.207	0.936	88.67%	Very High
2	Strategic direction	6.197	1.002	88.52%	Very High
3	Organizational culture	6.229	0.915	88.98%	Very High
4	Organizational Chart	6.173	0.930	88.19%	Very High
	Strategic planning	6.201	0.897	88.59%	Very High

It is clear from the table that the level of practice of achieving organizational excellence in the Yemeni private universities under study was very high, as it came in an arithmetic mean (6.201), with a standard deviation of (0.897) and a large percentage (88.59%), and that after achieving organizational culture it came in the highest rank in terms of The study sample agreed with an average of (6.229) and a standard deviation of (0.915) and a very high percentage of (88.98%). This is due to universities' knowledge of the importance of organizational culture indicators, which are considered one of the most important work priorities. Being linked to its growth and expansion in the labor market, the dimension of excellence in organizational structure came in fourth and last place with an average (6.173), standard deviation (0.930), and a high percentage (88.19%). This is attributed to the keenness of the administration of Yemeni private universities to clarify the powers, authorities and tasks of all its employees, and to inform them of everything It is new in terms of the organizational structure, which universities seek to constantly update according to various environmental variables, and this updating may be accompanied by shortcomings to some extent sometimes as a result of the rapid environmental changes surrounding them.

4.1. Hypotheses testing:

A. Testing the main hypothesis:

The main hypothesis states that "There is a statistically significant effect for strategic planning in achieving organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities." The main hypothesis (the effect of strategic planning on achieving organizational excellence) was examined using the path coefficients for the first main hypothesis, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Model estimation between strategic planning and organizational excellence

IV	Path	DV	R ²	Beta	T	P-Value
Strategic planning	-->	organizational excellence	0.476	0.889	59.856	0.000

The table shows that there is a statistically significant effect of strategic planning on organizational excellence, as the Beta value in the main path reached (890.8), which indicates the presence of a strong effect of strategic planning on the organizational excellence of the Yemeni private universities in the study sample. This means that assuming other variables are neutral, an increase in strategic planning by one degree will achieve (89%) of the characteristics of organizational excellence for the Yemeni private universities in the study sample, and this is reinforced by the (T) value, which reached (59.856), and the (p-value) of the coefficient The estimate is less than (0.001) and is statistically significant at a significance level less than (0.05), and therefore we accept the first main hypothesis. The value of R² in the main track of strategic planning and organizational excellence was (0.476); This indicates that strategic planning

explains (48%) of the changes occurring in the organizational excellence of the Yemeni private universities in the study sample, while (52%) is explained by other variables, which has moderate explanatory power. The quality of the model means an explanation of the phenomenon, and this is reinforced by the model's standard error of (0.023). The study agreed with the study of Omar (2019), which showed the existence of an impact of strategic planning on the performance of employees in Yemeni private universities, and the study of Othman (2017: 124), which showed that there is an influential relationship to strategic planning and competitive advantage and that organizations must rely on strategic planning the strategy for its future operations to obtain a competitive advantage helps it achieve its future goals, and the study of Al-Dajani (2017, p. 421), which showed the existence of a statistically significant relationship between the level of the role of strategic planning and the quality of the organizational performance of universities. The study of Aporia (2014, p. 178), showed the existence of a strong positive correlation with the percentage of standards for organizational excellence, meaning that there is a role for strategic planning in achieving organizational excellence. The more strategic planning is applied, the greater the chances of achieving standards for organizational excellence, and vice versa.

B. Testing the sub-hypotheses:

Testing the sub-hypotheses was performed as follows:

- The first sub-hypothesis states that: " There is a statistically significant effect of environmental analysis in achieving organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities."
- The second sub-hypothesis states that: " There is a statistically significant effect of strategic direction in achieving organizational excellence in private Yemeni universities."
- The third sub-hypothesis states that: "There is a statistically significant effect of strategic formulation in achieving organizational excellence in private Yemeni universities."

To test the hypotheses, the study data were analyzed using structural equation modeling using least squares after confirming its assumptions. It was found that there was a linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables, and the residuals were independent, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Model estimation between independent variables and organizational excellence

IV	Path	DV	Beta	T-value	P-Value
Environmental analysis	-->	Organizational excellence	0.159	2.446	0.015
Strategic direction	-->	Organizational excellence	0.518	5.956	0.001
Strategic formulation	-->	Organizational excellence	0.064	2.822	0.005

There was a statistically significant effect of environmental analysis on organizational excellence, as the beta value was (0.159); This means that assuming other variables are neutral, an increase in environmental analysis by one degree will help achieve (16%) of the organizational excellence characteristics of the Yemeni private universities under study, and this is reinforced by the value of (T), which reached (2.446), which is statistically significant at a level of significance less than (0.05)

Therefore, we accept the first sub-hypothesis of the main hypothesis, and this result agreed with the study of Othman (2017, p. 123), which showed that there is an influential relationship between environmental analysis and work satisfaction in Sudanese telecommunications organizations, and the study of Jarrar & Dwikat (2013), which confirmed that there is an impact Inter-analysis positively influences performance excellence. There was a statistically significant effect of strategic direction on organizational excellence, as the beta value was (0.518) This means that assuming other variables are neutral, an increase in strategic direction by one degree will achieve (52%) of the characteristics of organizational excellence for Yemeni private universities, and this is reinforced by the value of (T), which reached (5.956), which is statistically significant at a significance level of less than (0.05).

Therefore, we accept the second sub-hypothesis of the main hypothesis, and the study agreed with Omar's study (2019), which showed a positive effect of strategic orientation on the performance of employees in private Yemeni universities. The study by Othman (2017, p. 123), showed that there is a direct and influential relationship between vision, mission, and work satisfaction in Sudanese communications organizations, and the study by Siam (2010, p. 123), showed that there is a positive effect of strategy formulation on performance in civil society organizations.

There was a statistically significant effect of strategic formulation on organizational excellence, as the beta value was (0.253). This means that, assuming other variables are neutralized, an increase in strategic formulation by one degree will work to achieve (25%) of the characteristics of organizational excellence for Yemeni private universities, and this enhances the value of (T) which amounted to (2.822), which is statistically significant at a significance level less than (0.05), and therefore we accept the third sub-hypothesis of the main hypothesis. The study agreed with the study of Omar (2019), which showed a positive effect of strategic formulation on the performance of employees in private Yemeni universities, and the study of Siam (2010, p.123), who explained that there is a positive effect of strategic formulation on performance in civil society organizations.

5. CONCLUSION

The results showed that there are very high practices of strategic planning in the Yemeni private universities under study. The results of the study showed that there is a very high interest on the part of the Yemeni private universities under study in achieving organizational excellence. There is a strong positive impact of strategic planning on organizational excellence in the Yemeni private universities under study. There is a statistically significant positive effect of the dimensions of strategic planning on organizational excellence in Yemeni private universities, the field of study, and the highest achievement of strategic planning is the dimension of strategic orientation, followed by the dimension of environmental analysis.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Continuing the practice of strategic planning by private Yemeni universities and enhancing this practice using modern scientific methods in strategic planning to ensure improving the level of organizational excellence in the private Yemeni university's field of study. It is necessary to pay more attention to strategy formulation in Yemeni private universities than it is now, especially since it has an impact on organizational excellence and is the least practiced by Yemeni private universities.

Increase work on involving relevant workers in the environmental analysis process for the Yemeni private universities under study. Increased interest in involving the main relevant parties in preparing their mission for the Yemeni private universities under study. Focus on describing the goals of the Yemeni private universities under study with a kind of challenge and ambition. Increase interest in the results of environmental analysis in the Yemeni private universities under study by developing alternative strategies for emergencies. The need for the private Yemeni universities under study to strengthen their financial capabilities to face challenges and allocate a portion of their revenues to meet the requirements of expansion and growth. Working to enhance the capabilities of the Yemeni private universities under study by taking advantage of their available resources and developing their systems and policies in line with changes in the surrounding environment.

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